

Visualization Techniques and Tools for Developing Digital Twins of Ecosystems: State-of-the-Art and Selection

Adeela Ashraf
University of Amsterdam
Amsterdam, the Netherlands
adeela-97@hotmail.com
0000-0002-4914-2726

Robert G Belleman
Computational Science Lab
University of Amsterdam
Amsterdam, the Netherlands
R.G.Belleman@uva.nl
0000-0001-6576-8350

Zhiming Zhao
Multiscale Networked Systems
University of Amsterdam
LifeWatch Virtual Lab and Innovation Center
Amsterdam, the Netherlands
Z.Zhao@uva.nl
0000-0002-6717-9418

Abstract—A digital twin (DT) is a real-time digital copy of a physical entity. The interest in DTs has been an increasing trend in recent years in academia as well as industry, which includes ecosystems. DTs of ecosystems replicate the composition, behaviour, and functionality of real ecosystems, providing several advantages. With the highlighted importance of DTs in ecosystems, selecting the appropriate visualization techniques and tools becomes crucial.

Visualization techniques play an important role in DT systems for presenting the digital representation of the physical system and for supporting users to effectively explore the information of DTs. During the past decades, a large volume of work has been conducted in the context of scientific visualization; however, no overview exists that summarizes visualization techniques and tools of DTs of ecosystems. Therefore, this paper aims to fill this gap.

First, a systematic literature review is conducted to consolidate data types, visualization techniques, and tools that are used for DTs and ecosystems. To structure the consolidated visualization techniques the domains of application are identified. Requirements and challenges for DTs are identified similarly to assess the suitability of each visualization tool. Second, a selection tool is constructed using the results of the review such that a user can quickly assess what visualization technique and tool to select. The approach is applied to a use case.

Index Terms—digital twins, ecosystems, systematic literature review, visualization techniques, visualization tools, selection tool

I. INTRODUCTION

The digital twin (DT) is defined as a real-time digital copy of a physical entity [1]. First observed in 1970, the concept was introduced in 2002 by Grieves as part of product life-cycle management and described as a virtual product representing the data of a physical product [2], [3]. The National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) introduced the term in 2010 and in 2012 defined it as a high-fidelity simulation that reflects the state of a corresponding twin using historical data, real-time sensor data, and the physical model [4], [5]. In 2014, Grieves published the first white paper defining DTs as a three-dimensional model, consisting of a physical product, a virtual representation, and a bidirectional connection between the two

[6]. Using the three-dimensional model as a base, Tao et al. [7] define a five-dimensional model consisting of a physical entity, virtual model, services, data, and connections between the four components, see Fig. 1. The CIRP Encyclopedia of Production Engineering defines the DT using an eight-dimensional model consisting of integration breadth, connectivity mode, update frequency, CPS intelligence, simulation capabilities, digital model richness, human interaction, and product life-cycle [3], [8].

Fig. 1. The five-dimensional digital twin model, reproduced from Qi et al. [9].

The interest in DTs has been an increasing trend in recent years [3] in academia as well as industry, which includes ecosystems. DTs of ecosystems replicate the composition, behaviour, and functionality of real ecosystems, providing several advantages. The European Digital Twin of the Ocean (European DTO), part of the Horizon Europe program, is an interactive replica of the ocean providing data, models, and AI. Users are able to create applications for specific scenarios, allowing for a better understanding of the ocean, predicting outcomes, and making informed decisions around ocean policies [10]. Similarly, Destination Earth (DestinE) is a high-fidelity DT of the Earth that monitors, simulates and

predicts interactions between natural phenomena and human activities [11]. In general, DTs of ecosystems can improve collaboration and communication between different stakeholders by providing a common tool to use, and provide advantages to addressing problems such as climate change.

With the highlighted importance of DTs in ecosystems, selecting the appropriate visualization techniques and tools becomes crucial. Choosing the right techniques (e.g. 3D geometric modelling, network graphs, or pie charts) and tools (e.g. Unity3D, JavaScript, or WebGL) provides several advantages. Dashboards are efficient for the observation of key metrics, especially when working with large amounts of ecosystem data. Modelling can give a deeper understanding by illustrating different perspectives and degrees of granularity. The advantages of problem detection, dependency observations, and optimization are further enhanced as interpretation and analysis are made easier for the human eye. Not only is visualization important during construction, the need for visualization often continues after the completion of the DT in the form of maintenance.

In practice, selecting the right visualization techniques and tools often occurs by trial and error, adding or removing from the DT through iterative reviews and analysis. This however does not guarantee in finding the most optimal solution. Rogers et al. propose a visualization mapping space where visualization techniques are classified using a grid, see Fig. 2. Here, the horizontal axis denotes the dimension of the underlying data, whereas the y-axis is the dimension of the geometric primitive chosen to display the data. Choosing to display two-dimensional data in one dimension, for instance, suggests using contour maps, field vectors, or space curves [12]. For ecosystems, however, the effectiveness of visualiza-

Fig. 2. The visualization mapping space, reproduced from Rogers et al. [12].

tion is not only dependent on the dimension of the data, but on the requirements of the DT itself such as computing power, storage, or security among others. Visualization techniques play an important role in DT systems for presenting the digital representation of the physical system and for supporting users to effectively explore the information of DTs. During the past decades, a large volume of work has been conducted in the

context of scientific visualization; however, no overview exists that summarizes visualization techniques and tools of DTs of ecosystems.

Therefore, this paper aims to consolidate visualization techniques and tools for DTs and ecosystems, identify the domains where visualization techniques are applied, and review tools on consolidated requirements and challenges of DTs. This is done by conducting a systematic literature review and developing a selection tool that allows users to view and filter for specific use cases. By doing so, insight can be gained in selecting fitting techniques and tools for visualization in the context of DT construction of ecosystems.

The paper is structured as follows: Section II discusses related work to selecting visualization tools and techniques to construct DTs, where Section III describes the steps of the systematic literature review and construction of the selection tool. Section IV presents the results, including applying the findings to a use case. This is followed by a discussion and a conclusion in sections V and VI respectively.

II. RELATED WORK

This section discusses related work to selecting visualization techniques and tools for developing DTs of ecosystems. Due to the absence of literature on DTs of ecosystems, searches were conducted for related work on DTs and ecosystems separately.

For related work on ecosystems, Klein et al. describe a demand analysis approach for identifying representation types of ecosystems services (ES) information. Utilizing a survey, user demands for visualizing and communication are identified for integration into decision support systems [13].

Palomino et al. conduct a review on collaborative geospatial tools, developing a framework evaluating various functional aspects. A cluster analysis is applied to construct a topology of the tools, resulting in three primary clusters [14].

A paper by Lenters discusses GEOGEAR, an interactive tool for generating integrated geospatial data products for ecosystem research. In order to create geospatial data products, a qualitative literature study is conducted on tools, software, and publications [15].

A pattern is observed for related work on DTs. First, the DT is defined, often as a model or system. Requirements and challenges are highlighted from the definition and addressed by introducing technologies, which describe a functionality such as communication, verification, or storage. Lastly, technologies are elaborated by listing techniques, tools, or both. For the scope of this paper, only visualization-related work will be discussed in detail.

Fuller et al. [16] discuss in a categorical literature review the enabling technologies, challenges, and open research for AI, IoT, and DTs. Here, the DT is defined as a three-dimensional model. Different levels of data integration of DTs are discussed to distinguish between the types of data flows among the connections between the physical and virtual models.

Enabling technologies for DTs are classified using four functional domains originating from the field of IoT: application, middleware, networking, and object. The application

domain discusses visualization as an enabling technology, listing Simulink and Twin Builder as visualization tools [16].

Kritzinger et al. [17] define the DT as a three-dimensional model in a categorical literature review. To create an overview of DTs in manufacturing, reviewed papers are classified on type of work and level of data integration, where an area or areas of focus and technologies are identified. The results show two papers that discuss visualization technologies, focused on production, planning, and control. No tools listed [17].

Qi et al. [9] use the five-dimensional model to identify technologies and tools. The summary introduces a framework that lists various technologies for each dimension. Visualization technologies are listed with data and the virtual component. Interface technology is closely related to visualization and is listed with communication. Visualization elements can appear in other components, such as service.

A theoretical system for the virtual component is discussed by introducing four sub-models: A geometric, physical, behavioural, and rule model. The geometric model concerns the virtualization of the physical component in terms of its shape, structure, and geometric information. The physical model adds to the geometric model and contains entity features and constraints, such as surface roughness, material type, and performance. The behavioural model describes the behaviours of the physical model in simulation, such as response to changes. Lastly, rule modelling adds to the behavioural model by including historical data, expert knowledge, and predefined logic. Following this system, various tools are listed.

A systematic research paper by Tao et al. [18] analyses and classifies studies on digital modelling according to the four sub-models of the theoretical system of the virtual component, as mentioned by Qi et al. [9]. In addition, six modelling aspects are introduced for the theoretical system: construction, assembly, fusion, verification, modification, and management. Results show that almost half of the selected studies focus on visualization in terms of functionality for the DT. Following this, enabling visualization technologies and tools are specified. Visualization technologies are found within model construction, specifically geometric and physical modelling, where various tools are listed.

A state-of-the-art survey of DT by Lim et al. [19] approaches listing tools by addressing multiple perspectives of DTs, such as engineering product lifecycle management and DT simulation improvements.

The studies demonstrate varying approaches to listing visualization techniques and tools for DTs and ecosystems. However, no studies focus on visualization techniques and tools specifically for DTs of ecosystems, or focus predominantly on visualization itself. To close this gap, this paper aims to consolidate visualization techniques and tools for DTs ecosystems, identify the domains where visualization techniques are applied, and review tools on consolidated requirements and challenges of DTs.

III. METHOD

This section discusses the methods used to consolidate visualization techniques and tools for constructing DTs of ecosystems. In order to do this, two steps are taken: First, a systematic literature review is conducted to consolidate data. Second, a selection tool is constructed using the results of the review.

A. Systematic Literature Review

1) *Research questions:* Several factors need to be taken into consideration in order to conduct a literature review. As mentioned in Section II, not many papers exist that focus on the visualization techniques and tools of DTs of ecosystems. To combat this, the scope can be broadened by surveying visualization techniques and tools for DTs and ecosystems separately, combining the findings.

Second, for clarity and ease of selection, the found visualization techniques require categorization. Therefore, the domains using the visualization techniques are identified.

Third, selecting the suitable technique or tool from an overview depends on the requirements or challenges of the DT itself. Therefore, the visualization techniques and tools also require assessment on the requirements and challenges of DTs of ecosystems. The following research questions (RQs) can be formulated, see Fig. 3 for an overview.:

- 1) What visualization techniques and tools exist for DTs?
- 2) What visualization techniques and tools exist for ecosystem research?
- 3) What visualization techniques and tools exist for DTs of ecosystems?
- 4) What are the requirements and challenges of digital twins?
- 5) To what domains are visualization techniques for DTs of ecosystems applied?
- 6) How do the visualization tools address the requirements and challenges of DTs of ecosystems?

Fig. 3. Relationships between the research questions.

2) *Literature selection*: To answer the research questions as described in Section III-A1, a systematic literature review is conducted for RQs one, two, and four, for which the following search strings are constructed respectively:

1. [digital twin or related keywords] AND (visualization OR visualisation)
2. ecosystem AND (visualization OR visualisation)
3. [digital twin or related keywords] AND (requirements OR challenges)

Here, related keywords are problem-solving environment, human-in-the-loop, computational steering, living simulation, interactive visualization, intelligent maintenance system, human-system integration, and cyber-physical system.

3) *Application selection criteria*: Criteria are introduced to identify primary studies from the collected literature. Primary studies are defined as studies that meet all inclusion (IN) and exclusion (EX) criteria. These are defined as follows:

- IN1 The focus of the paper must be relevant to the RQ.
Rationale: The main focus of the paper must be relevant to the RQ such that sufficient information can be extracted.
- IN2 The paper must be peer-reviewed.
Rationale: To ensure a degree of validity, the paper must be peer-reviewed.
- IN3 The paper must be directly available.
Rationale: For the sake of an efficient literature search, only papers that are directly available must be considered.
- EX1 The paper must not be a secondary or tertiary study (survey, review, etc.).
Rationale: Indirect sources of literature are excluded to ensure a degree of quality from the extracted data.
- EX2 The paper must be written in English.
Rationale: Several relevant papers exist that are partially translated into English, but are not complete. To ensure a degree of quality and for the sake of efficiency, these papers are excluded.

4) *Data consolidation*: Primary studies are identified by applying the selection criteria. For each primary study of RQs one and two, data type(s), visualization technique(s), and visualization tool(s) are recorded. Here, the following concept is introduced: To apply data to DTs, visualization techniques and tools need to be considered. To consider what tools are deemed suitable, the visualization technique needs to be selected first, which relies on the type of data present. Therefore, an order is established in recording data: A data type is applied to one or more visualization techniques, which is realized by using one or more visualization tools. For primary studies of RQ four, any requirement or challenge is recorded.

B. Selection Tool

To construct the selection tool, some factors are considered, such as wide-range accessibility to users, interaction, and the ability to quickly gain an overview of the consolidated data.

React [20] provides an interactive web-based solution and is selected for construction. For displaying the consolidated data, a graph-based solution is chosen, which is constructed using vis.js [21]. A pipeline is constructed to process the consolidated data, where Python scripts are used to convert raw data to various data structures in JSON format. See Fig.4 for an overview.

Fig. 4. Data pipeline that processes input for the selection tool.

IV. RESULTS

This section provides the results of the systematic literature review and selection tool as described in Section III.

A. Results Systematic Literature Review

Referring to Fig. 3, the results of the review are discussed in four parts:

- 1) Visualization techniques and tools of DTs and ecosystems (RQs 1-3)
- 2) Requirements and challenges of DTs (RQ4)
- 3) Identifying domains for applied visualization techniques for DTs of ecosystems (RQ5)
- 4) Addressing requirements and challenges of DTs using visualization tools (RQ6)

1) *Visualization techniques and tools for DTs and ecosystems*: In total, 30 primary studies are found discussing visualization techniques and tools for DTs and ecosystems. As discussed in Section III-A4, data from each paper is extracted and classified on a trial-and-error basis into three categories: data type, visualization technique, and visualization tool. See Figs. 5, 6, and 7 for an overview of the results.

Here, data types are further classified as:

- **Abiotic Data**: Data involving non-living that affect organisms, e.g. climate, water, and atmosphere.
- **Behavioural Data**: Data regarding interaction between individuals.
- **Biotic data**: Data involving living organisms, e.g. plants, bacteria, and human beings.
- **Geometric Data**: Data regarding size, shape, and other relevant information of an object, represented in 3D.
- **Geospatial Data**: Data revolving around a specific location in the real world, e.g. GIS data.

- 12) **Safety:** Protection from risks for humans by verification or issuing certificates.
- 13) **Standardization:** Alignment in understanding between different domains, stakeholders, or goals.
- 14) **Economic value:** Demonstrating the business or monetary value of the system.
- 15) **Usability:** Ease of operation by humans.
- 16) **Collaboration:** Ability for multiple stakeholders to make adjustments to the system or model.

Fig. 8. Occurrence of requirements and challenges of digital twins.

3) *Identifying domains for applied visualization techniques for DTs of ecosystems:* Utilizing the results from RQs 1-3, the following domains are identified:

- Aerospace Engineering
- Agriculture
- Augmented Reality
- Astronomy
- Ecosystem Modelling
- Environmental Decision Support Systems
- Extended Reality
- Food Web
- Forest Ecosystems
- Freshwater Ecosystems
- Geographic Information System
- Healthcare
- Information Analysis
- Landscape Ecology
- Manufacturing
- Marine Ecosystems
- Microbiology
- Smart Cities
- Soundscape Ecology
- Virtual Reality
- Visualization

See Fig.9 for an overview.

4) *Addressing requirements and challenges of DTs using visualization tools:* Combining the results from the systematic literature review, visualization tools are assessed against the requirements and challenges of DTs. To accomplish this, additional information is acquired from the tool providers, such

Fig. 9. Heatmap depicting occurrence of identified domains among applied visualization techniques for DTs of ecosystems.

as the official websites. A scoring system is introduced to assess each tool:

- 1) **Suitable (+):** The tool fulfills the requirement or challenge without additional effort.
- 2) **Moderately suitable (+/-):** The tool fulfills the requirement or challenge, but within specific terms and/or requires extra effort to be fulfilled.
- 3) **Unsuitable (-):** The tool does not fulfill the requirement or challenge, or requires huge amounts of effort to be fulfilled.
- 4) **Blank ():** The requirement or challenge is not applicable to be assessed by the visualization tool.

B. Results Selection Tool

The results of the systematic literature review are used as input for a web-based selection tool¹² providing an interactive network graph, see Fig. 10. Starting with an empty graph, the user is able to build a network graph using the left sidebar. Multiselect boxes display data types, visualization techniques, and visualization tools, which are depicted as nodes in the graph. Edges between two nodes represent their appearance in the same paper, where the thickness of the edge represents the number of papers. Nodes of the same category (e.g. two data type nodes) appearing in the same paper are depicted with a dashed line, and can be toggled on or off from the sidebar left. The graph utilizes a ForceAtlas2 layout. Lastly, for techniques and tools, nodes of the same category are further categorized such that clustering is available from the sidebar.

Interaction with the graph is possible by selecting nodes or edges, highlighting any directly connected neighbour edges

¹https://adeelaashraf.github.io/visualization_DTs_ecosystems

²https://github.com/visualisationlab/visualization_DTs_ecosystems

Fig. 10. Demonstration of the selection tool where the network graph depicts all data types, visualization techniques, and visualization tools in the dataset. Information on the selected node 'Geospatial Data' is depicted in the right sidebar.

if present. Upon selecting a node for edge, the right sidebar displays all related papers with relevant information. For visualization tools, assessment using requirements and challenges of DTs is displayed as well, showing a rating and possible link to official sources where possible. Lastly, users are able to download the full dataset for further viewing of the used data.

C. Use Case: Notebook-as-a-VRE (NaaVRE)

To use the selection tool for constructing visualizations for DTs of ecosystems, an approach is described as follows:

- 1) **Identification:** Considering the context of the DT, data type(s), domain(s), requirement(s), and challenge(s) are identified.
- 2) **Input:** The data type(s) and domain(s) are used as input for the selection tool. Any visualization tools of interest are inserted as well.
- 3) **Inspection:** A network graph is created, where nodes and edges of interest are inspected. Additional information is inspected in the right sidebar. Using the identified requirement(s) and challenge(s), the assessment of visualization tools of interest is inspected as well.
- 4) **Selection:** Following the inspection, the most optimal visualization tool is selected. The most optimal visualization technique is selected by considering the presented techniques within the identified domain(s), or following from a selected and relevant visualization tool.

The approach is applied to a use case. Notebook-as-a-VRE (NaaVRE) [22] is a virtual research environment realized as a Jupyter extension, allowing an efficient search for research resources, remote cloud automation and managing workflows. Users are able to containerize cells using Docker, use containers to construct a workflow, and deploy the workflow on a Kubernetes cluster. While the NaaVRE allows for efficient large-scale computations, visualization of the workflow result is not possible remotely. As visualization can be of importance in virtual research environments, further expansion of the NaaVRE for visualization of workflows is to be desired.

The NaaVRE demonstrates an example in need of remote visualization. LiDAR data of the Netherlands were collected

during the third Dutch national airborne laser scanning flight campaign for ecosystem structure, height, and complexity [23]. LiDAR point clouds are processed using the Laserchicken framework [24] remotely, and locally visualized as shown in Fig.11.

Fig. 11. Visualization of processed LiDAR data using the Laserchicken framework, retrieved from Zhao et al. [22]. The LiDAR data were collected during the third Dutch national airborne laser scanning flight campaign for ecosystem structure, height, and complexity.

To extend the NaaVRE for visualization of workflows, the approach is applied as follows:

- 1) The LiDAR data is identified as sensor data, abiotic data, geospatial data, and landscape data. As domain, visualization is identified. For requirement(s) and challenge(s), main points of concern include Data Capacity (ability to handle large datasets), Integration (adequate compatibility with the NaaVRE architecture, which is accessed by the web), and Collaboration (ability to be used by multiple users).
- 2) The identified data is inserted into the tool. As no specific visualization tools are of interest, all visualization tools are selected. For ease of viewing, all techniques and tools are clustered.
- 3) A network graph is created, see Fig.12. Three visualization technique nodes are depicted: Immersive Visualization Techniques, 3D Geometric Modelling, and 2D plots. From here, all directly connected visualization are inspected with the identified requirement(s) and challenge(s) in mind.
- 4) Following the inspection, only web-based tools are considered, which are mainly used for 2D plots. Selected as visualization technique, it is found that OpenLayers is the most suitable visualization tool that addresses the identified requirement(s) and challenge(s).

V. DISCUSSION

This section discusses key findings from the results, contributions of the paper, and limitations. The systematic literature review displays a pattern of usage of certain data types, visualization techniques, and tools. Data types not specifically associated with ecosystems, such as Metadata or Geometric data, are more commonly used with 3D Geometric Modelling

Fig. 12. Selection tool demonstrating the network graph, constructed using sensor data, abiotic data, geospatial data, and landscape data.

and Immersive Visualization Techniques. In turn, associated visualization tools used are commonly found as standalone Desktop applications, with less flexibility for integration with other tools or frameworks.

Data types associated with ecosystems are commonly visualized using 2D plots, such as histograms or bar plots, and utilize visualization tools such as Python, R or Jupyter Notebook to achieve this. Requirements and challenges for DTs of ecosystems are found to prioritize functionality of the DT itself, such a real-time processing, high degree of integration and Data Capacity. Requirements and challenges such as Safety and Collaboration are not prioritized, giving the implication that the functioning of the DT is more valued than its experience by users.

This paper has contributed in consolidating visualization techniques and tools for DTs of ecosystems and creating a selection tool for DT construction. In doing so, selection patterns are highlighted, and a method is presented for DT construction. However, such consolidation is limited to the amount of papers reviewed, and requires more data collection for a more complete consolidation. No validation is conducted in terms of user experience by users for the selection tool.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presents an approach to selecting visualization techniques and tools for DTs of ecosystems. A systematic literature review is conducted, consolidating data on data types, visualization techniques, visualization tools, requirements, and challenges of DTs. A selection tool is constructed such that visualization techniques and tools can be selected.

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